

Relationship between Analog Theorems for the Dirichlet Eta Function and the Riemann Zeta Function

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Abstract: The Dirichlet zeta function and Riemann zeta function are the most important special functions in the area of analytic number theory. This paper presents analog theorem for the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann zeta function, and its relationship.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-16] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and also in the summation of series involving the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann zeta function [17-19]. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [20].

2. Harmonic Series, Dirichlet Eta Function, and Riemann Zeta Function

The harmonic series is defined by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{9} + \dots$$

and the alternative harmonic series is shown below:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} - \frac{1}{8} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n}.$$

The Dirichlet eta function relating to the alternative harmonic series is defined by

$$\eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} - \frac{1}{8^s} + \dots$$

The Dirichlet eta function $\eta(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $\text{Re}(s) > 0$.

The Riemann zeta function for all complex numbers is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \dots$$

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $\text{Re}(s) > 1$.

Theorem 2.1: The sum of alternative harmonic series is equal to $\ln 2$.

$$i.e. \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Proof. This theorem is proved using the infinite geometric series as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } S &= 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots \\ \Rightarrow xS &= x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + x^8 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Then, } (S - xS) = 1 \Rightarrow (1 - x)S = 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{1 - x} = S.$$

$$i.e. \frac{1}{1 - x} = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots$$

Integrating on both sides with respect to x :

$$\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx.$$

First, let us find the solution of $\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx$.

$$\text{Let } u = 1 - x; \quad du = -dx; \quad dx = -du.$$

$$\text{Then, } \int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = - \int \frac{1}{u} du = - \ln u = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\text{Now, } \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow x + \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^5}{5} + \frac{x^6}{6} + \frac{x^7}{7} + \frac{x^8}{8} + \dots = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} \dots = - \ln(1 - x) \Rightarrow - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} = \ln(1 - x).$$

Substituting $x = -1$ on both sides:

$$- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = \ln(1 - (-1)) \Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

3. Analog Theorems for $\eta(s)$ and $\zeta(s)$

The analog theorem for the Dirichlet eta function is given below:

$$\textbf{Theorem 3.1:} \quad \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = - \ln 2.$$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the geometric series:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(-\frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots \right)$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = -\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} - \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} - \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots$$

Simplifying this equation using the geometric series:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = -\left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} - 1\right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} - 1\right) - \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} - 1\right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} - 1\right) - \dots$$

$$\text{Here, } \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^s} - 1\right) = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{k}} - 1 = \frac{k}{k-1} - 1 = \frac{k-k+1}{k-1} = \frac{1}{k-1} \text{ for } k = 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$$

Now, we conclude that

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = -1 + \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{5} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = -\ln 2.$$

The analog theorem for the Riemann zeta function is given below:

$$\textbf{Theorem 3.2: } \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}$$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the geometric series:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}\right) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots\right)$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{6^s} + \dots$$

Simplifying this equation using the geometric series:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} - 1\right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} - 1\right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} - 1\right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} - 1\right) + \dots$$

$$\text{Here, } \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^s} - 1\right) = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{k}} - 1 = \frac{k}{k-1} - 1 = \frac{k-k+1}{k-1} = \frac{1}{k-1} \text{ for } k = 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$$

Now, we conclude that

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}.$$

4. Relationship between Analog Theorems

The following theorem provides the relationship between analog theorems for the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann zeta function.

$$\textbf{Theorem 4.1: } \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) + \eta(s) - 2) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1)$$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem as follows:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) + \eta(s) - 2) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1 + \eta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1)$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} + (-\ln 2) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \dots\right) + \left(-1 + \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} - \dots\right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} =$$

From the above equation, we get

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) + \eta(s) - 2) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1).$$

Hence proved.

5. Conclusion

In the article, the author has proved several analog theorems for the Riemann zeta function. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2017) Computational Modelling for the Formation of Geometric Series using Annamalai Computing Method. *Jñānābha*. Vol.50(2), pp 128-131. <https://doi.org/10.58250/jnanabha.2020.50215>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2015) A Novel Approach to ACM-Geometric Progression. *Journal of Basic and Applied Research International*, Vol.2(1), pp 39-40.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2019) Extension of ACM for Computing the Geometric Progression. *Journal of Advances in Mathematics and Computer Science*, Vol. 31(5), pp 1-3. <https://www.doi.org/10.9734/jamcs/2019/v31i530125>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) Summations of Single Terms and Successive Terms of Geometric Series. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4085922>.
- [5] Annamalai, C. (2017) Computational Modelling for the Formation of Geometric Series using Annamalai Computing Method. *Jñānābha*. Vol.47(2), pp 327-330.
- [6] Annamalai, C. (2022) Summations of Single Terms and Successive Terms of Geometric Series. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4085922>.
- [7] Annamalai, C. (2022) Sum of Geometric Series with Negative Exponents. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4088497>.
- [8] Annamalai, C. (2019) Computation of Series of Series using Annamalai's Computing Model. *OCTOGON MATHEMATICAL MAGAZINE*, Vol. 27(1), pp 1-3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4088497>.

- [9] Annamalai, C. (2022) Annamalai's Binomial Identity and Theorem. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4088497>.
- [10] Annamalai, C. (2022) Novel Binomial Series and its Summations. *SSRN* 4078523. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4078523>.
- [11] Annamalai, C. (2022) My New Idea for Optimized Combinatorial Techniques. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4078523>.
- [12] Annamalai, C. (2022) A Binomial Expansion equal to Multiple of 2 with Non-Negative Exponents. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4116671>.
- [13] Annamalai, C. (2022) Differentiation and Integration of Annamalai's Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4110255>.
- [14] Annamalai, C. (2023) Computational Technique for Geometric Series with Radicals. *TechRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.24311773.v1>.
- [15] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computational Method and Calculus for the Summation of Geometric Series and Binomial Expansions. *Cambridge Open Engage*. <https://www.doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53-v15>.
- [16] Annamalai, C. (2022) Sum of the Summations of Binomial Expansions with Geometric Series. *Cambridge Open Engage*. <https://www.doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53>.
- [17] Annamalai, C. (2024) Riemann Zeta Function and Dirichlet Eta Function relating to Alternative Harmonic Series. *Cambridge Open Engage*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2024-bcsk5>
- [18] Annamalai, C. (2024) Computation of Analog Theorem for Dirichlet Eta Function and Riemann Zeta Function. *Cambridge Open Engage*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2024-zl78p>.
- [19] Annamalai, C. (2024) Computer Program in C Programming Language for Calculating the Value of Euler Product equal to the Riemann Zeta Function. *Cambridge Open Engage*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2024-ljqlb>.
- [20] Annamalai, C. (2010) Application of Exponential Decay and Geometric Series in Effective Medicine. *Advances in Bioscience and Biotechnology*, Vol. 1(1), pp 51-54. <https://doi.org/10.4236/abb.2010.11008>.